

Correlation of some haemostatic parameters with length of stay and outcome in the Intensive Care Unit of a tertiary hospital in Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Patients with life-threatening illnesses and injuries are managed in intensive care units (ICUs), where they receive optimal care from a team of specialists. These patients have a myriad of altered haemostatic parameters, which can be associated with poor prognosis. This study aims to determine the relationship between some haemostatic parameters with length of stay and outcome in patients admitted into the ICU of a tertiary health facility in Zaria, Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** This was a prospective observational study in which patients admitted into the ICU of ABUTH Zaria were recruited consecutively. Their socio-demographic characteristics, indications for admission and haemostatic parameters were assessed. Length of stay and outcome were also determined. Blood samples were collected to determine haemostatic parameters. The patients were followed up for two (2) weeks to determine the outcome. Data were analysed using SPSS Version 20.0. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant. Approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of ABUTH Zaria. **Results:** Thirty-nine (39) participants were enrolled on the study. Their mean age was 32.7 ± 15.8 , and females constituted the majority of participants. Medical conditions were the main reason for ICU admission in our study, accounting for 20/39 (51.3%). The mean duration of ICU stay (days) among participants was 3.8 ± 1.9 , with a range of 1 to 7 days, and the majority of participants, 18/39 (46.2%), were discharged home directly from the ICU. There was a correlation between the duration of stay in the ICU and outcomes, as well as some haemostatic parameters. **Conclusion:** ICU admissions during the study period were predominantly among young individuals, with females constituting the majority. The deranged haemostatic parameters are associated with a longer ICU stay. Baseline haemostatic evaluation on patients admitted into the ICU is recommended.

Keywords: Haemostatic Parameters, Intensive Care Unit, Prognosis, Tertiary Hospital, Nigeria.

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Introduction

Patients with life-threatening illnesses and injuries are referred to as critically ill. These encompass patients with varying medical, surgical, and obstetric conditions, burns, among other cases. They require close and constant attention from teams of specialists, with their clinical parameters monitored closely. As such, they are managed in the intensive care units (ICUs) where such services are provided. This category of patients represents a significant source of morbidity and mortality even in the developed world with near adequate manpower for health and sophisticated medical gadgets.¹ The burden of ICU morbidity and mortality is particularly higher in resource-limited settings like Nigeria and other developing countries

owing to poor manpower, inadequate medical equipment and other ICU supportive facilities.¹ Altered haemostatic parameters, such as prolonged global coagulation times, reduced levels of coagulation inhibitors, and elevated fibrin degradation products, have been reported in ICU patients. These parameters, when deranged, are associated with poor prognosis, and they are very strong independent predictors of ICU mortality.² Haemostasis itself is a complex, tightly regulated process where a balance is obtained between procoagulant and anticoagulant mechanisms.³ This is often deranged in critically ill patients for multifactorial reasons, sometimes even in a way where thrombotic and hemorrhagic conditions can co-exist simultaneously.³ The risk of bleeding and thromboembolic complications varies greatly depending on the patients' population, grade of organ dysfunctions, nature and severity of disease, pre-existing conditions and the scope of medical interventions given.⁴

Studies have reported that thrombotic events are common in critically ill patients, both before and after ICU admission, even in patients receiving routine thromboprophylaxis.^{5,6} In particular, the development of pulmonary embolism or lower extremity deep vein thrombosis is associated with increased mortality. The risk of non-leg venous thrombosis is comparatively lower and not necessarily associated with higher mortality. Risk scores for hospitalised medical patients, such as the Padua Prediction Score, are available to approximate an individual patient's risk for thrombosis.⁶ However, applicability in high-risk ICU patients is limited, which makes patient assessment and clinical research on strategies to prevent or stop thromboembolic complications difficult.⁷ Specifically for ICU patients, the ICU-venous thromboembolism score was developed, including six independent predictors, which include:

- i. Central venous catheterization.
- ii. Immobilization for greater than or equal to 4 days.
- iii. Prior history of venous thromboembolism.
- iv. Mechanical ventilation.
- v. Haemoglobin concentration during hospitalization of less than or equal to 9 g/dL.
- vi. Platelet count at admission of less than $250 \times 10^9/L$.⁸

Studies have also shown that platelet count and haemostatic parameters are stronger independent predictors for ICU mortality than the standard

composite scoring systems, such as the Acute Physiology and Chronic Evaluation (APACHE) II score.^{8,9} Although these haemostatic parameters are readily measurable and their derangements can be easily detected. Most studies of how they affect ICU stay and outcome are from developed countries. Locally relevant data on the haemostatic parameters of ICU patients and their impact on length of stay and outcomes will drive evidence-based prognostication and management of this unique group of patients. This study aimed to determine the relationship between some haemostatic parameters and length of stay and outcome in critically ill patients admitted into the ICU of Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTH), Zaria, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

This was a prospective observational study in which patients admitted into the ICU of ABUTH Zaria, a Tertiary Health facility in Zaria, Kaduna State, Northwestern Nigeria, were recruited consecutively. The minimum sample size was determined using the formula (Araoye, 2003).¹⁰

$$n = z^2pq / d^2$$

where:

n = minimum sample size

p = prevalence of ICU admission in a Nigerian Tertiary Hospital 3% (Nwasor *et al.*, 2016).¹

q = 1 - p

z = 1.645 for a 90% confidence level

d = 0.05

Therefore n = 31

However, with consideration of the non-response rate of 20%

$$\text{Adjusted sample size (fn)} = \frac{n}{1-x}$$

Where x is the non-response rate and is equal to 20%

Therefore, adjusted sample size = $31/0.8 = 38.75$

Hence, the minimum sample size for this study is 31 with an adjusted 20% attrition rate giving a total of 39 participants.

Patients that had blood transfusion within 24 hours prior to ICU admission and those that were on anticoagulant therapy were excluded. Their socio-demographic characteristics, indications for admission and haemostatic parameters (Prothrombin Time (PT), Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (APTT) and Thrombin Time (TT)) were assessed. Length of stay and outcome were also determined. The hospital is a tertiary health facility that serves a cosmopolitan mix of clients from across the country. Its 17 clinical departments are served by a four-bed open-ward intensive care unit for the management of critically ill patients.

A proforma was used to collate information since most patients would not be able to respond to questionnaires at the time of ICU admission. Venous blood samples were collected in sodium citrate containers for the determination of PT, APTT and TT. The patients were followed up for two (2) weeks to determine the outcome, and a repeat of the laboratory tests above was done.

Data were collated and analysed using SPSS Version 20.0. These were summarised using frequencies, means, modes, medians, quartiles, percentiles and charts where applicable. Mann-Whitney U and Wilcoxon Signed-rank tests were used to determine associations between unpaired and paired observations, respectively. The Spearman Rank Test was used to assess correlations. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant. Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee (HREC) of ABUTH Zaria. All proformas were coded at the point of collection, and confidentiality was maintained.

Definition of Terms

The following definitions were utilised for the purpose of this study:

- i. **Prolonged ICU stay:** ICU stay for more than 14 days.¹
- ii. **Outcome / End point:** Either death or discharge (with or without morbidity).

Results

Thirty-nine (39) participants were enrolled. The mean \pm SD age of the study participants was 32.7 ± 15.8 years. Females constituted 21/39 (53.8%) of the participants. Medical conditions were the main reasons for ICU admission in our study, while burns were the least common, at 2/39 (5.1%) (Table 1). Amongst the various medical conditions, septicaemia was the commonest medical condition leading to ICU admission (Table-1). The mean \pm SD duration of ICU stay (days) among participants was 3.8 ± 1.9 , with a range of 1 to 7 days, and the majority of participants, 18/39 (46.2%), were discharged home directly from the ICU (Figure 1). The haemostatic parameters of the participants are presented in Table 2. The control values for the Prothrombin Time (PT), Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time (APTT) and Thrombin Time (TT) were 14, 35 and 10 seconds, respectively (Table 2). There was a statistically significant correlation between the duration of stay in ICU and the PT Ratio (Table 3).

Table-1: Distribution of ICU-admitted cases under category

Category	Cases	Freq	(%)
Obstetric Complications	Uterine rupture with PPH	2	5.1
	Severe eclampsia	5	12.8
	DIC	2	5.1
Medical Conditions	DKA	1	2.6
	MI	2	5.1
	DTB with pneumonia	2	5.1
	Emphysema	3	7.8
	RVD with sepsis	1	2.6
	Pulmonary	1	2.6
	Embolism	8	20.5
Orthopaedics/Trauma	Septicaemia		
	RTA with head injury	5	12.8
	Multiply-injured patient	2	5.1
Postoperative cases	SCD post cholecystectomy	2	5.1
	Ruptured ectopic pregnancy	1	2.6
	Burns	2	5.1
Total		39	100.0

Key: PPH-Postpartum Haemorrhage, DIC-Disseminated Intravascular Coagulopathy, DKA-Diabetic Ketoacidosis, MI-Myocardial Infarction, DTB-Disseminated Tuberculosis, RVD-Retroviral Disease, RTA-Road Traffic Accident, SCD-Sickle Cell Disease.

Figure-1: Distribution of outcome in the participants

The Kruskal-Wallis test was performed to assess the relationship between haemostatic parameters (PT, APTT, and TT) across indication categories, and the test revealed a statistically significant difference in APTT across indication categories (Table 4).

Table-2: Haemostatic Parameters of Participants (n =39)

Variable	Median (IQR)	Ratio
PT (seconds)	15(5.0)	1.1
APTT (seconds)	37(11.0)	1.1
TT (seconds)	10.0(5.0)	1.0

PT = Prothrombin Time, APTT= Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time, TT= Thrombin Time

Table-3: Correlation of Duration of stay in ICU with Haemostatic Parameters

	PT-Ratio	APTT-Ratio	TT-Ratio
Duration of stay in ICU (Days)	0.476**	-0.026	0.085
r value	-0.002	0.877	0.606

PT: Prothrombin Time, APTT; Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time, TT: Thrombin Time

Table 4: Distribution of Haemostatic Parameters across Categories of Indications for Admission

	PT (seconds)					APTT (seconds)					TT (seconds)				
	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E
25th percentile	14.0	13.8	11.0	13.5	15.0	36.0	34.3	46.0	30.5	37.0	8.5	9.0	10.0	8.0	11.0
Median	15.0	15.0	11.0	14.0	15.0	36.0	36.0	46.0	33.0	37.0	10.0	11.0	13.0	9.0	11.0
75th percentile	16.0	22.0	21.5	14.0	15.0	48.0	38.0	54.0	33.0	37.0	10.5	17.0	16.5	9.0	11.0
Kruskal Wallis Test Statistic	4.712					11.499					7.558				
p-value	0.318					0.021					0.109				

Categories of Indications for Admission: A = Obstetrics, B = Medical, C = Orthopaedics/Trauma, D = Postoperative, E = Burns, PT = Prothrombin Time, APTT = Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time, TT = Thrombin Time

Post Hoc analysis was conducted on the parameter with statistically significant differences across categories of indications for admission into the ICU (APTT) and the test revealed that patients admitted into the ICU due to Orthopaedic/Trauma indications had statistically significantly higher median APTT values compared to Postoperative cases (46 seconds versus 33 seconds, p = 0.018) (Table-5).

There were no statistically significant relationships between the admitting haemostatic parameters (PT (p=0.221), APTT (p=0.796), TT (P=0.943)) across the outcome categories. However, there was also a statistically significant relationship between the indications for admission and outcome (X² = 15.520, p = 0.050), and the majority of ICU patients with orthopaedic/trauma admissions died in the ICU (6/7, 85.7%) (Table 6).

Discussion

The mean age of the participants in our study was 32.7 years. This is similar to what was reported by Rajadhyaksha *et al* in India, where they reported 33.7 years.¹¹ A contrasting result was observed by

Onyekwulu *et al* in Nigeria, where the mean age was 38.2 years.¹² Age, though important in inpatient segregation and management, has no direct bearing on the pattern of admission, as emergencies in most cases do not respect age. This study showed a female preponderance, which is a contrast to what Onyekwulu *et al*¹² found. The difference cannot be explained by any factor, as critical cases are almost always emergencies with no gender predilection. However, obstetric complications, being the second most common indication for admission into the ICU, can be a contributing factor to female preponderance. The distribution of cases admitted to the ICU is similar to that reported by Rajput *et al*. in India, with medical conditions accounting for the majority of cases and burns accounting for the least. 13, 14 A contrasting finding was reported by Salami *et al* in Nigeria, where general surgery and neurological cases predominated, with medical cases being the least.¹⁵

The mean duration of ICU stays (days) for participants in this study was 3.8 ± 1.9. This is in contrast to what was reported by Ojiakor *et al*, Tobi *et al.*, and Onyekwulu *et al.*, all in Nigeria.^{12,14,16}

Table 5: Post Hoc Pairwise comparison of APTT across categories of indications

APTT Vs Categories of Indication	Test Statistic	Standard Error	p-value
Postoperative cases-Medical conditions	11.800	7.011	0.924
Postoperative cases-Burns	-13.500	10.338	1.00
Postoperative cases-Obstetric complications	16.000	7.814	0.406
Postoperative cases-Orthopaedic/Trauma	24.429	7.814	0.018
Medical conditions-Burns	-1.700	8.398	1.00
Medical conditions-Obstetric complications	4.200	4.973	1.00
Medical conditions-Orthopaedic/Trauma	-12.629	4.973	0.111
Burns-Obstetric complications	2.500	9.080	1.00
Burns-Orthopaedic/Trauma	10.929	9.080	1.00
Obstetric complications-Orthopaedic/Trauma	-8.429	6.053	1.00

APTT = Activated Partial Thromboplastin Time

The short stay of the patients in our study could be attributed to the managing team's expertise in a moderately equipped unit that facilitates swift transfer to the open ward or discharge home after stabilisation. None of the patients in this study had a prolonged ICU stay, defined as ≥ 14 days.¹⁷ This could be explained by the limited number of beds in the ICU in ABUTH Zaria, where once a patient is stabilised, he/she would be moved to the open ward to create space for other critically ill patients. Prolonged stay is associated with increased utilisation of resources, increased hospital care costs, and may also contribute to increased morbidity and mortality.

In the ICU, many patients develop haemostatic abnormalities ranging from abnormal clotting tests to frank bleeding. Coagulopathy was defined as PT > 18 sec and/or PTTK > 36 sec.¹⁷ The median PT, PTTK and TT of our study were similar to those of Gil et al., while contrasting higher values were reported by Puranik et al.^{17,18}. There was a statistically significant correlation between the duration of ICU stay and the PT ratio. This is in contrast to the study by Gilhooly *et al.* where they found no relationship.¹⁹ There is a relationship between PT/PTTK and TT across the categories of indication, and the test revealed a statistically

significant difference in APTT across categories of indications for admission. This is similar to what was reported while a contrasting result was reported Gilhooly et al.¹⁹ Post Hoc analysis was conducted on the parameter with statistically significant differences across categories of indications for admission into the ICU (APTT) and the test that patients admitted into the ICU due to Orthopaedic/Trauma indications had statistically significant higher median APTT values compared to Postoperative cases (46 seconds versus 33 seconds, $p= 0.018$). The higher values of prolonged APTT seen in Orthopaedic/Trauma patients could be due to massive bleeding, which results in an uncompensated loss of coagulation factors, particularly in patients with major blood loss, where intravascular volume is rapidly replaced with crystalloids, colloids, and red cells without simultaneous administration of coagulation factors.¹⁹

The study revealed fairly normal haemostatic values and significant correlations with the length of ICU stay and outcome. The majority of the participants in the study were discharged home directly from the ICU; however, there was a mortality rate of 28.2%. This finding is similar to that of Osinaike et al. in a multi-centre Nigerian study, with a mortality of 23%, although their study was restricted to postoperative cases.²⁰ Higher mortalities were reported by Eze *et al* in Abakaliki, Southeast Nigeria.²¹ The high mortality rates in our ICUs can be explained by late presentation of patients, dearth of well-trained staff and lack of adequate supportive equipment, as well as the nature of the illness and comorbidities at the time of admission.

Conclusion

ICU admissions during the study period were predominantly among young individuals, with females constituting the majority, and the average length of stay was approximately four days. Deranged haemostatic parameters are associated with increased duration of ICU stay and high mortality.

We therefore recommend the following:

1. Patients admitted into the ICU should have the baseline haemostatic parameters irrespective of the indication for admission and those with deranged parameters should be very aggressively managed to avoid mortality.
2. A multicenter study where the haemostatic parameters can be explored in a large population of patients is recommended.

Table 6: Distribution of Outcome by Indications for Admission

Indication for Admission		Outcome			Total
		1	2	3	
A	Count	1.0	4.0	2.0	7.0
	% within row	14.3 %	57.1 %	28.6 %	100.0 %
	% within column	9.1 %	22.2 %	20.0 %	17.9 %
B	Count	4.0	11.0	5.0	20.0
	% within row	20.0 %	55.0 %	25.0 %	100.0 %
	% within column	36.4 %	61.1 %	50.0 %	51.3 %
C	Count	6.0	0.0	1.0	7.0
	% within row	85.7 %	0.0 %	14.3 %	100.0 %
	% within column	54.5 %	0.0 %	10.0 %	17.9 %
D	Count	0.0	2.0	1.0	3.0
	% within row	0.0 %	66.7 %	33.3 %	100.0 %
	% within column	0.0 %	11.1 %	10.0 %	7.7 %
E	Count	0.0	1.0	1.0	2.0
	% within row	0.0 %	50.0 %	50.0 %	100.0 %
	% within column	0.0 %	5.6 %	10.0 %	5.1 %
Total	Count	11.0	18.0	10.0	39.0
	% within row	28.2 %	46.2 %	25.6 %	100.0 %
	% within column	100.0 %	100.0 %	100.0 %	100.0 %

Categories of Outcome: 1 = Died, 2 = Discharge, 3 = Transferred to other wards

Categories of Indications for Admission: A = Obstetrics, B = Medical, C = Orthopaedics, D = Postoperative, E = Burns

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Author's contributions:

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FM Grema: Data acquisition and drafting the article
SM Mukhtar: Data acquisition and interpretation of data

M Mahdi: Data acquisition and interpretation of data

S Yuguda: Revising the article for important intellectual content and final approval of the version to be published.

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